

Current issues with data sovereignty in the UK

Health Data Research (HDR UK) and DARE UK lens

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Our mission

HDR UK's mission is to accelerate trustworthy data use to enable discoveries that improve people's lives

Our 20-year vision is for large-scale data to benefit every interaction with patients, every clinical trial and every biomedical discovery, and to transform public health

Core funders

What are we all about?

Improving health and boosting UK science by making it easier for researchers to find, access and use diverse, high-quality data

Providing leadership to fix difficult technical problems, by creating innovative solutions needed for researchers to use large-scale data safely and securely

Accelerating & streamlining health data science by developing open collaborations that connect data, people and organisations across the UK and internationally

Sensitive data: affecting people, communities, and populations...

Data linkage: safely connecting sensitive data to benefit people, communities and populations...

Vision

For all research and innovation to benefit from seamless, secure use of diverse sensitive data, at a pace, efficiency and scale approaching that of the open data ecosystem, that revolutionises research productivity and accelerates research to deliver public good

Mission

To put the UK at the forefront of sensitive data research and innovation by assembling the tools, technologies and standards needed to streamline secure data linkage and use

FUNDED BY

UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) – the UK’s largest public funder of data and research innovation – through the [UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure programme](#).

DELIVERED BY

[Health Data Research UK \(HDR UK\)](#) and [Administrative Data Research UK \(ADR UK\)](#).

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UK Landscape – DARE UK recent survey

- Number of TREs has increased
- Several very large TREs (>500 projects), with many much smaller ones

UK Landscape – DARE UK recent survey

- TREs are run by a range of different sectors in the UK e.g.
 - Several by different groups within the National Health Service (NHS)
 - The Office of National Statistics
 - Many different universities (often in partnership with the NHS who are the data controllers)
 - Industry also provide TRE services
- TREs support both unconsented and consented research studies
 - Large research collected cohorts (such as UK Biobank and Our Future Health) provide access TREs

Figure 2. Breakdown of respondents by organisation type.

UK Landscape - legislation

- UK has aligned with GDPR following Brexit
- Another key piece of legislation is the Common Law of confidentiality
- Health is devolved – with data controller status given to the individual 4 Nations: Scotland, Wales, England and Northern Ireland
 - At a devolved nation level **secondary care** health data is collected for administrative purposes – and can be used for secondary research purposes within TREs (with CAG approval)
 - Unconsented health data does not travel between the devolved nations
 - Secondary care data is also held by individual NHS Boards/Trusts – much greater depth than captured nationally – and can also be used for research purposes with CAG approval)
 - The data controller for primary care data is the GPs themselves – who need to consent for the data to be used for research purposes
 - Very complex access routes

TREs are distributed across the UK

Figure 4. Geographical distribution of survey respondents across the UK.

Digital Economy Act (DEA)

- A key bit of legislation covering secondary usage of administrative/government data for research – but HEALTH data generally excluded
- There are 8 DEA accredited environments within the UK (including the Office of National Statistics) that support 1000+ research projects per year – using TREs
- Some health data can be linked and access, but it is very complex which forms can and can't be linked

Digital Economy Act 2017

The screenshot shows the UK Statistics Authority website. The header includes the logo and the text 'UK Statistics Authority Statistics for the Public Good'. A navigation menu contains 'Home', 'About us', 'News', 'Boards and committees', and 'Correspondence'. The breadcrumb trail reads: 'UK Statistics Authority > Digital Economy Act: Research and Statistics Powers > Digital Economy Act > List of Digital Economy Act Accredited Processing Environments'. The main heading is 'List of Digital Economy Act Accredited Processing Environments'. Below this, it states: 'Digital Economy Act (DEA) 2017 accredited processors are accredited for the functions of:'. A bulleted list follows: 'linking, matching, curating and de-identifying of data (preparation); and/or storing and provision of access to de-identified data (provision)'. At the bottom, it says: 'If your organisation is interested in becoming accredited under the Digital Economy Act 2017, please email Research.Accreditation@statistics.gov.uk'. Below the text is a map titled 'Digital Economy Act Accredited Processing Environments' showing the locations of these environments across the UK and Ireland. The map includes labels for Glasgow, Edinburgh, Isle of Man, Dublin, Manchester, Birmingham, and London. Neighboring countries like Denmark, Netherlands, Belgium, and Germany are also partially visible.

Networks of TREs – more likely to federate...

- 4 National TREs who can provide secondary care high level health data access – one for each devolved nation
- New networks of TREs being funded and emerging – including national and regional TREs for each devolved nation e.g.
 - Scottish Network of Safe Havens (for the past 10+ years)
 - UK SeRP – Wales and Northern Ireland (for ~5 years)
 - English Secure Data Environment Network (about 3 years old)
- DARE SATRE specification for TREs widely adopted

Federation across TREs

Data Pooling

Happens where information governance allows this
e.g. sharing across networks within same devolved
nation or ONS
(eyes on)

Meta Analysis

Often happens when
information governance
doesn't allow data pooling
(eyes on)

Federation across TREs

Federated Analytics & Federated Learning

Increasingly happening – but many TREs
reject as don't want to install many different
federation tools
(eyes off)

Investigation of new federation models

Standards

- SATRE specification for a TRE
- OMOP common data model
- 5 Safes TES
- 5 Safes RO-Crate
- Front door TRE, mesh network standards for connecting TREs on a per project basis

Where to next?

- Health Data Research Service (HDRS) - £600M investment, just launched, focused on access to health data for research
- National Data Library (NDL) - ~£100M investment, focused on open data, and intergovernmental department access to sensitive data
- Work is underway to bring health data into a revised "DEA" accreditation scheme
- ENTRUST – Heavily involved in this project
- EHDS – UK needs to align...

Thanks for listening

